

BACKGROUND

Cold-formed structural steel profiles are currently used in various industrial sectors, namely in rack structures for logistics warehouses because they are flexible, economic and sustainable. On the other hand, storage and retrieval (S/R) machines that carry weighty goods at high speeds over these structures, raises fatigue issues in those structures. Currently in EN 1993-1-3 standard there is no reference about fatigue design of structural solutions made of cold-formed thin-walled profiles. **FASTCOLD** project intends to develop a new fatigue regulation for cold-formed structural steel details, with special focus on logistics industry.

OBJECTIVE

This work consisted in conducting static/monotonic, slip/monotonic and fatigue tests in **double-covered bolted butt joints** with “snuggle tight” bolts. The data analyzed will be used in a new fatigue design regulation of bolted connections for cold-formed structural steels.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Figure 1 illustrates the types of investigated specimens. In summary:

- Two structural steel grades and three surface treatments:
S355MC (without coating);
S350GD (with zinc coating and zinc coating plus paint);
- Two types of geometries (1+1 and 4+4 bolts);
- Two preload levels (25%×70%Fu and 70%Fu);
- Two plate thickness (2 and 3mm).

Figure 1 – Specimen's geometries tested under monotonic, static and slip, and fatigue loading.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MONOTONIC/ STATIC TESTS

Static monotonic tests in bolted joints and **tensile tests** in S355MC and S350GD steel were performed (Figure 2). **Numerical simulations** with Von Mises plasticity model were performed to generate load-displacement (P-d) curves for comparison with experimental results (Figure 3). Besides P-d curves, **failure modes** were also evaluated (Figure 4).

Figure 2 – Tensile experimental conventional curves.

Figure 3 – Experimental vs. numerical load-displacement curves.

Figure 4 – Experimental failure mode vs. numerical equivalent plastic strain fields at ultimate loads: left, 1+1 bolted joint; right, 4+4 bolted joint. A: S355MC; B: S350GD

MONOTONIC/ SLIP TESTS

Slip tests were performed in accordance to the **EN 1090-2** standard (see Figure 5) [1]. Table 1 shows the results obtained by slip tests.

Table 1– Average and characteristic slip factors obtained according to EN 1090 .

Slip Tests EN 1090-2	Uncoated	Zinc coated	Zinc coated + painted
Average Slip Factor	0.28	0.31	0.14
Coef. Of Var. (%)	(21%)	(18%)	(15%)
Characteristic Slip Factor	0.16	0.20	0.09

Figure 5 – Experimental setup for slip tests.

FATIGUE TESTS

Fatigue tests were performed under R=0.1 (Figure 6):

- **Snug tight and preloaded M16 bolts** (1+1 and 4+4 bolts) (preliminary tests);
- **Snug tight M12 bolts** for three stress amplitude levels.

M12 bolts fatigue data were analyzed statistically accordingly the **ASTM E739** standard [2] and compared with **Eurocode 3** S-N curve [3].

Figure 6 – Average experimental S-N curve according to ASTM standard [2] from data of snug tight M12 bolts. Comparison with EC3 Class 90 S-N Curve and other bolted joints configurations.

CONCLUSIONS

- **Maximum and minimum differences** between experimental and numerical ultimate loads of monotonic/static tests were **11%** and **0.35%**, respectively;
- **Zinc coating induces changes** on mechanical behaviour of the steel, namely on Yield and ultimate strength, and ductility;
- The slip factors for Zinc Coated + Paint were **extremely low**; uncoated and zinc coated steel revealed **very similar slip factors**;
- Slope of actual **S-N curves** proposed in **EC3** for non-preloaded bolted joints is **significantly different** than experimental S-N curves for snug tight bolted joints.

REFERENCES

- [1] CEN, EN 1090-2: Execution of steel structures and aluminium structures – Part 2: Technical requirements for steel structures (2008).
- [2] ASTM, ASTM E739: Standard Practice for Statistical Analysis of Linear or Linearized Stress-Life (S-N) and Strain-Life (ε-N) Fatigue Data. ASTM Standards, (2012).
- [3] CEN, EN 1993-1-3: Eurocode 3: Design of Steel structures – part 1-9: Fatigue (2005).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

